

Sample 01a

Greyscale Image

PARC Phases

		area %
	{Pb-rich}	0.0002
	{Si}	35.1
	{Fe}	31.9
	{Ca}	7.3
	{Al, Si}	5.8
	{Si, Fe}	3.4
	{Al, Si, K}	3.0
	{Na, Al, Si}	2.2
	{Si, Ca LoP}	2.0
	{Si, Ca HiP}	1.5
	{Mg, Ca}	0.9
	{Al, Si, Ca}	0.7
	{Si, K}	0.6
	{Na, Si}	0.5
	{Mg, Al, Si}	0.5
	{Mg, Si}	0.4
	{Ca, Fe}	0.4
	{Mg, Si, Ca}	0.3
	{Na, Si, Cl}	0.3
	{S, Ca}	0.3
	{Al, Si, Fe}	0.2
	{Si, Ca, Fe}	0.2
	{Cl}	0.2
	{Mg, Al, Si, Ca}	0.1
	{Si, P}	0.1
	{Si, Fe}	0.1
	{Cl}	0.1
	{Si, Cl}	0.1
	{Si, S, Ca}	0.1
	{Al}	0.1
	{P, Ca}	0.1
	{Mg, Fe}	0.1
	{Si, Ca, Ti}	0.1
	{Na, Cl, Ca}	0.1
	{Ti}	0.1

area % is excl. empty spectra

Source materials (detailed)

	area %
Sinter	1.3
Pellet	9.3
Ore preparation undifferentiated	19.3
Ore preparation Mn-rich	0.1
Ore / hot metal	1.6
BOF converter slag	0.5
BOF converter slag slopping	0.1
Slag BOF converter or desulph	0.3
Desulph slag	0.0
Ca-aluminate slag	0.0
Blast furnace slag	0.1
Dolomite residue - iron- and steelmaking	0.7
Olivine flux	0.1
Ca-carbonate or hydroxide - diverse	0.0
Ca-carbonate or hydroxide - iron- and steelmaking	1.5
Dolomite residue or refractory MgO	0.0
MgO with spinel - refractory	0.0
Tundish gunning mass	0.0
Alumina	0.1
Fe-FeOx with Zn-compounds	0.0
Rich in Zn-compounds	0.0
Fe-metal rich	0.1
Coal and cokes or soil	1.9
Carbon rich with steelmaking phases	1.3
Carbon rich - other	1.1
Cement or BOF converter	1.9
Cement	1.6
Gypsum or anhydrite	0.1
Ti-rich paint	0.1
Ba-sulphate bearing	0.0
Na-Ca-silicate rich	0.0
Al-corrosion/salts	0.0
Salt or salt layer	0.0
Qz-clay-fsp-mica GT 60 pct	32.3
Qz-clay-fsp-mica 30-60 pct	23.7
Misc silicates including natural	0.0
Possible ore gangue silicate	0.0
Apatite	0.0
Ca-Al-silicate dominated	0.0
Ca-Al-silicate with Ca-silicate	0.0
Na-sulphate rich	0.0
Pb-rich GT 40 pct	0.0
Unassigned with GT 30 pct Na-rich chloride	0.0
Unassigned with GT 30 pct other chloride	0.0
Unassigned with detected Pb-rich	0.0
Unassigned other	0.9

Source categories

	area %
Site - ore	30.0
Site - ore / hot metal	1.6
Site - slag	0.8
Site - slag, urban	0.1
Site - flux	0.7
Site - flux / slag, + natural	0.0
Site - flux / slag	1.5
Site - flux / refractory	0.0
Site - refractory	0.1
Site - scrap	0.0
Urban + site - scrap	0.1
Site - coal & cokes; + natural + urban	1.9
Site - carbon-rich other	1.3
Site - carbon-rich other, + natural + urban	1.1
Urban, rarely site - slag	1.9
Urban	1.9
Natural salt - immediate	0.0
Natural mineral background	32.3
Natural mineral background mixed site / urban	23.7
Natural source - immediate + via site	0.0
Unknown	0.0
Pb-rich various	0.0
Unassigned (w/wo partial chloride cover)	0.9

All Populations

Populations containing 1 or more Pb pixels

Grains containing 1 or more Pb pixels

Phases in grains containing 1 or more Pb pixels

Sample 01b

Greyscale Image

PARC Phases

		area %
	{Pb-rich}	0.0384
	{Si}	36.0
	{Fe}	28.8
	{Ca}	7.0
	{Al, Si}	6.2
	{Al, Si, K}	3.1
	{Si, Fe}	3.1
	{Na, Al, Si}	2.6
	{Si, Ca LoP}	1.8
	{Mg, Ca}	1.5
	{Si, Ca HiP}	1.3
	{Mg, Si}	1.0
	{Mg, Al, Si}	0.9
	{Al, Si, Ca}	0.8
	{Si, K}	0.5
	{Mg, Si, Ca}	0.5
	{Na, Si}	0.5
	{Ca, Fe}	0.5
	{Mg, Al, Si, Ca}	0.3
	{S, Ca}	0.3
	{Na, Si, Cl}	0.3
	{Al, Si, Fe}	0.2
	{P, Ca}	0.2
	{Si, Ca, Fe}	0.2
	{Mg, Al, Si, Fe}	0.2
	{Cl}	0.2
	{Cl}	0.1
	{Si, S, Ca}	0.1
	{Mg, Fe}	0.1
	{Ti}	0.1
	{Si, Cl}	0.1
	{Si, Fe}	0.1
	{Mg, Si, Fe}	0.1
	{Mn}	0.1
	{Al}	0.1

area % is excl. empty spectra

Source materials (detailed)

	area %
Sinter	1.1
Pellet	7.2
Ore preparation undifferentiated	18.8
Ore preparation Mn-rich	0.1
Ore / hot metal	1.2
BOF converter slag	0.7
BOF converter slag slopping	0.6
Slag BOF converter or desulph	0.2
Desulph slag	0.3
Ca-aluminate slag	0.0
Blast furnace slag	0.0
Dolomite residue - iron- and steelmaking	1.8
Olivine flux	0.5
Ca-carbonate or hydroxide - diverse	0.0
Ca-carbonate or hydroxide - iron- and steelmaking	2.4
Dolomite residue or refractory MgO	0.0
MgO with spinel - refractory	0.0
Tundish gunning mass	0.0
Alumina	0.0
Fe-FeOx with Zn-compounds	0.0
Rich in Zn-compounds	0.0
Fe-metal rich	0.1
Coal and cokes or soil	1.8
Carbon rich with steelmaking phases	0.6
Carbon rich - other	1.2
Cement or BOF converter	0.5
Cement	1.1
Gypsum or anhydrite	0.1
Ti-rich paint	0.1
Ba-sulphate bearing	0.0
Na-Ca-silicate rich	0.0
Al-corrosion/salts	0.0
Salt or salt layer	0.0
Qz-day-fsp-mica GT 60 pct	34.4
Qz-day-fsp-mica 30-60 pct	24.6
Misc silicates including natural	0.0
Possible ore gangue silicate	0.0
Apatite	0.1
Ca-Al-silicate dominated	0.0
Ca-Al-silicate with Ca-silicate	0.0
Na-sulphate rich	0.0
Pb-rich GT 40 pct	0.0
Unassigned with GT 30 pct Na-rich chloride	0.0
Unassigned with GT 30 pct other chloride	0.0
Unassigned with detected Pb-rich	0.0
Unassigned other	0.6

Source categories

	area %
Site - ore	27.1
Site - ore / hot metal	1.2
Site - slag	1.8
Site - slag, urban	0.0
Site - flux	2.2
Site - flux / slag, + natural	0.0
Site - flux / slag	2.4
Site - flux / refractory	0.0
Site - refractory	0.0
Site - scrap	0.0
Urban + site - scrap	0.1
Site - coal & cokes; + natural + urban	1.8
Site - carbon-rich other	0.6
Site - carbon-rich other, + natural + urban	1.2
Urban, rarely site - slag	0.5
Urban	1.4
Natural salt - immediate	0.0
Natural mineral background	34.4
Natural mineral background mixed site / urban	24.6
Natural source - immediate + via site	0.1
Unknown	0.0
Pb-rich various	0.0
Unassigned (w/wo partial chloride cover)	0.6

All Populations

Populations containing 1 or more Pb pixels

Grains containing 1 or more Pb pixels

Phases in grains containing 1 or more Pb pixels

Sample 01c

Greyscale Image

PARC Phases

		area %
	{Pb-rich}	0.0003
	{Fe}	32.5
	{Si}	32.1
	{Ca}	7.4
	{Al, Si}	7.0
	{Si, Fe}	3.5
	{Na, Al, Si}	2.9
	{Al, Si, K}	2.8
	{Si, Ca LoP}	1.7
	{Mg, Ca}	1.6
	{Si, Ca HiP}	1.2
	{Na, Si}	0.6
	{Al, Si, Ca}	0.6
	{Si, K}	0.6
	{Mg, Al, Si}	0.5
	{Mg, Si, Ca}	0.5
	{S, Ca}	0.5
	{Mg, Si}	0.4
	{Ca, Fe}	0.3
	{Al, Si, Fe}	0.3
	{Na, Si, Cl}	0.3
	{Ti}	0.2
	{Mg, Al, Si, Ca}	0.2
	{Cl}	0.2
	{Si, S, Ca}	0.2
	{Si, Ca, Fe}	0.1
	{P, Ca}	0.1
	{Si, Fe}	0.1
	{Cl}	0.1
	{Si, Cl}	0.1
	{Al}	0.1
	{Mg, Fe}	0.1
	{Al, Fe}	0.1
	{Na, Al, Si, Cl}	0.1
	{Mg, Si, Fe}	0.0

area % is excl. empty spectra

Source materials (detailed)

	area %
Sinter	0.7
Pellet	10.0
Ore preparation undifferentiated	21.9
Ore preparation Mn-rich	0.0
Ore / hot metal	0.6
BOF converter slag	0.1
BOF converter slag slopping	0.3
Slag BOF converter or desulph	0.0
Desulph slag	0.0
Ca-aluminate slag	0.0
Blast furnace slag	0.0
Dolomite residue - iron- and steelmaking	2.0
Olivine flux	0.0
Ca-carbonate or hydroxide - diverse	0.0
Ca-carbonate or hydroxide - iron- and steelmaking	2.0
Dolomite residue or refractory MgO	0.0
MgO with spinel - refractory	0.0
Tundish gunning mass	0.0
Alumina	0.0
Fe-FeOx with Zn-compounds	0.0
Rich in Zn-compounds	0.0
Fe-metal rich	0.3
Coal and cokes or soil	1.8
Carbon rich with steelmaking phases	0.3
Carbon rich - other	1.2
Cement or BOF converter	1.1
Cement	1.4
Gypsum or anhydrite	0.0
Ti-rich paint	0.2
Ba-sulphate bearing	0.0
Na-Ca-silicate rich	0.0
Al-corrosion/salts	0.0
Salt or salt layer	0.0
Qz-clay-fsp-mica GT 60 pct	32.5
Qz-clay-fsp-mica 30-60 pct	23.0
Misc silicates including natural	0.0
Possible ore gangue silicate	0.0
Apatite	0.0
Ca-Al-silicate dominated	0.1
Ca-Al-silicate with Ca-silicate	0.0
Na-sulphate rich	0.0
Pb-rich GT 40 pct	0.0
Unassigned with GT 30 pct Na-rich chloride	0.0
Unassigned with GT 30 pct other chloride	0.0
Unassigned with detected Pb-rich	0.0
Unassigned other	0.5

Source categories

	area %
Site - ore	32.6
Site - ore / hot metal	0.6
Site - slag	0.4
Site - slag, urban	0.0
Site - flux	2.0
Site - flux / slag, + natural	0.0
Site - flux / slag	2.0
Site - flux / refractory	0.0
Site - refractory	0.0
Site - scrap	0.0
Urban + site - scrap	0.3
Site - coal & cokes; + natural + urban	1.8
Site - carbon-rich other	0.3
Site - carbon-rich other; + natural + urban	1.2
Urban; rarely site - slag	1.1
Urban	1.6
Natural salt - immediate	0.0
Natural mineral background	32.5
Natural mineral background mixed site / urban	23.0
Natural source - immediate + via site	0.0
Unknown	0.1
Pb-rich various	0.0
Unassigned (w/wo partial chloride cover)	0.5

All Populations

Populations containing 1 or more Pb pixels

Grains containing 1 or more Pb pixels

Phases in grains containing 1 or more Pb pixels